

PERFORMANCE
Science with Society for Mission Cancer

D6.1 DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION, AND COMMUNICATION (DEC) PLAN

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PERIFORMANCE

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The T6.1 **Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) Strategy** aims to design and implement a comprehensive framework for communicating, disseminating, and exploiting the results of the PERFORMANCE project.

The success and impact of a project of this nature - which aims to ensure that cancer research and developments, in line with technological advances such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the European Health Data Space (EHDS), are applied in an ethical, equitable and transparent manner- depends on the scale of the efforts to reach the variety of agents and stakeholders involved. To achieve this aim, a plethora of communication and dissemination activities and channels will be implemented and created during the project's lifetime.

This requires the definition of robust and coherent strategies, tools, and processes to ensure that knowledge, results, and best practices are effectively transferred to all relevant audiences.

Accordingly, the main objective of this D6.1 DEC Plan is to establish the measures necessary to ensure that PERFORMANCE meets its objectives and achieves the expected impact. Thus, it provides an overview of the dissemination and communication materials and mechanisms designed to keep all target stakeholder groups informed about the project's progress, planning, and outcomes—ultimately increasing visibility, transparency, and cooperation among partners and interested parties.

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan include:

- Objectives and purpose
- Target groups
- Key messages
- Activities for implementation of the plan - Materials and tools
- Measuring impact
- Communication Team
- Time and phases

Overall, this plan outlines the actions and channels that will foster engagement with target audiences and stakeholders throughout the project duration. Additionally, it establishes the indicators required to monitor and evaluate the effective implementation of all communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities.

INTRODUCTION

PERIFORMANCE aims to promote **active public engagement** to improve the **impact, ethics and equity** of **EU Cancer Mission**, ensuring that progress and solutions are consistent with societal values, fairness and public trust, with a special focus on the use and deployment of **advanced technologies** and **infrastructures in cancer**. Our goal is to navigate the complexities and ethics of research and advances, such as AI and the European Health Data Space (EHDS), facilitating equitable transitions and promoting social innovation within the EU ecosystem and geography.

The present **Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication plan** intends to serve as a roadmap that will allow the PERIFORMANCE project to maximize its impact.

In this sense, PERIFORMANCE is one of the first projects to incorporate an ethical dimension into its methodology for EU Mission implementation. It not only aims to present its results to groups interested in or directly involved in cancer research, but it seeks to drive meaningful transformations within cancer research and care ecosystems. This transformation will be grounded in the recognition and integration of local innovation systems, industry, governments, biobank networks, and new or traditionally excluded stakeholders, among others, ensuring that their needs, perceptions, aspirations, values, and capacities are considered throughout the process. By doing so, PERIFORMANCE will contribute to the development of stronger, more responsive cancer and health policies, shaping the European landscape of cancer research and emerging technologies with trust, inclusivity, and accessibility as fundamental guiding principles.

Such approach demands for the diversification of the communication and dissemination strategy: different messages for diverse audiences, with varied formats and singular channels. Thus, this plan offers a proposal to combine and articulate materials and messages in accordance with the targeted audiences, and the objectives established with each of them, as well as to evaluate the impact that either the project or its results would have on the EU Cancer Mission research and innovation system, and its agents and policies.

It is noted that the plan should be considered a living document that will be adapted to new developments, needs, and knowledge gained during the PERIFORMANCE project. In any case, its framework follows the Grant Agreement 101216808 – PERIFORMANCE conditions and commitments, especially those compiled in Annex 1 (i.e. Description of Action, DoA, Parts A and B), as well as those emerged in the discussions following the project Kick-Off (11 September 2025) and subsequent meetings, widening views, approaches and relevant actors.

PERIFORMANCE's dissemination, exploitation and communication plan addresses these different approaches by integrating them into the following elements of its strategy definition:

- Objectives and purpose (“why?”)
- Target groups and key audiences (“who?”)
- Key messages (“what?”)
- Communication, dissemination and exploitation materials and tools - Methods (“how?”)
- Measuring impact - Methods (“how well?”)
- Communication Team - Methods (“With who?”)
- Activities for implementation of the communication plan - Time (“when?”)

GENERAL PRINCIPLES AND IMPLICATIONS of the STRATEGY DEFINITION

The present plan integrates three actuation areas that must be described so that the correct measures can be articulated within each of them. These areas are communication, dissemination and exploitation. Each of these areas entails different audiences, objectives, messages and instruments.

● **What is communication?** *“Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange”* (EU RESEARCH PROGRAMME, 2021-2027).

The general aim of communication is to impact on society as a whole and on audiences considered to be essential to the project, in order to attract the best experts, share best practices, promote the project’s activities and results; and trigger new collaborations & opportunities. To do that, it is necessary that the information distributed via communication activities are:

- ✓ **Relevant:** Both society and the identified specific groups must consider it useful and see its implications and impact relevant for their scenarios and contexts.
- ✓ **Accessible:** Regarding the need of a clear and comprehensible language to explain diverse complexities.
- ✓ **Attractive:** The target is to reach groups and audiences that are not necessarily linked to the project. The capacity of generating contents, formats and attractive messages is essential to ensure their involvement in the project and, therefore, maximize the impact.

It is based on the development of materials and channels such as project website, social media accounts, press media, non-scientific articles, video, digital/print flyers, etc.

● **What is dissemination?** *“The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium. It is a process of promotion and awareness-raising of the research results in a targeted way.”* (EU, 2021-2027).

Dissemination actions are aimed at facilitating effective knowledge transfer and promoting the practical implementation of project results. The primary target audience is not the general public, but rather stakeholders and professionals who can directly apply these results in their own work, such as researchers, clinicians, industry actors, local agents, and policymakers. Consequently, the information distributed through dissemination activities must be:

- ✓ **Trusted**, as these audiences rely on robust and credible evidence to inform decisions, guide research developments and innovation, and support changes in practice or policy.
- ✓ **Reliable**, to ensure that the results are perceived as scientifically sound, methodologically rigorous, and compliant with relevant ethical and regulatory standards, thereby fostering confidence in their adoption.
- ✓ **Practice-oriented**, required to translate scientific knowledge into actionable insights, tools, or recommendations that can be readily integrated into real-world contexts.

Relevant materials and tools in this regard range from scientific publications and academic outputs to workshops to exchange views and visions, joint actions with other EU/international projects, participation in

European/international events, training and capacity-building activities, and guidelines to support evidence-based public policies, among others.

● **What is exploitation?** *“The utilization of research in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities”* (EU, 2021-2027).

Within the project approach, exploitation can be of a different nature: social, political, practical application, etc. Therefore, the information distributed via exploitation activities must be:

✓ **Sustainable:** addressed to ensure the project’s sustainability and extending its impact beyond the project's lifetime.

✓ **Open and usable:** Within an open-access and co-created framework, the focus should be on how the project's results are used. The project should be designed for adoption and adaptation in different contexts and scenarios, and made accessible to members of the project team, as well as to different external stakeholders and interested parties.

In this regard, the training and capacity-building activities, as well as the exploitation of knowledge transferred in the Cookbook will enable the implementation of best practices and suitable adaptations to a varied localisations, contexts and socio-economic scenarios.

According to these three actuation areas, the definition of objectives will follow, aiming to avoid overlapping activities, maximizing the use of available resources, and correctly orientating the activities to the different stakeholders in the project, choosing the right channels and formats to have an impact on them.

OBJECTIVES and PURPOSE (“why?”)

In this context, of transformation of stakeholder engagement, PERIFORMANCE **Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication plan** aims to achieve the following general objectives:

COMMUNICATION

- To **communicate PERIFORMANCE’s objectives, activities, and progress clearly, attractively and transparently** to diverse stakeholder groups, fostering inclusiveness, mutual understanding, commitment, and trust throughout the project lifecycle.
 - To **optimise the flow of information** between the defined stakeholders and the institutions participating in the project, using the most suitable tools and channels, and adapting language, format, and messaging to each audience. This approach ensures clarity, inclusiveness, and effective two-way communication throughout the project.
- ➔ PERIFORMANCE’s aims, processes, and outputs will be accessible and understandable to diverse audiences, since materials would be tailored to each group’s language, expectations, information and needs. This approach will enhance informed participation, strengthen stakeholder interest, and foster meaningful collaboration throughout the project.

DISSEMINATION

PERIFORMANCE has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N. 101216808.

- To **facilitate the practical implementation** of project results, PERIFORMANCE will promote ongoing **interaction, networking, and structured dialogue** among stakeholders and key beneficiaries. These exchanges will help reveal the specific structures, strengths, vulnerabilities, needs, aspirations, values, and capacities of different local and regional ecosystems and agents. Such insights will be integrated into the design and execution of the project's initiatives, ensuring they are context-responsive and co-created with those directly involved.
 - To promote **wide and effective use of project outcomes**, all research findings, new knowledge, and best practices on stakeholder engagement will be openly distributed and shared, using open sources and tools, and FAIR practices -when possible-, enabling its translation into actionable recommendations within research institutions, biobanks, health systems, and policy frameworks. Thus, allowing its prompt integration into organisational practices, operational workflows, and strategic decision-making.
- ➔ Dissemination activities will focus not only on sharing findings, but also on actively inviting feedback and co-generation of knowledge. This includes organising interactive events (workshops, webinars, focus groups), open calls for initiatives, and collaborative platforms that enable stakeholders to contribute insights, priorities, and interpretations of emerging results, ultimately generating more trusted, sensitive, and practice-oriented conclusions.
- ➔ Develop and disseminate practical, reliable, and trustworthy outputs—such as case studies, good-practice compendia, methodological guidelines, and user-friendly toolkits—that provide organisations with ready-to-use resources for strengthening their engagement processes.

EXPLOITATION AND OUTREACH

- To drive **sustainable and systemic change in cancer research and innovation ecosystems**, PERIFORMANCE will encourage the **uptake, reuse, and adaptation of its outputs** across diverse organisational and regional contexts. The project will translate its insights into concrete assets that improve the design, structure, governance, and implementation of stakeholder-engagement initiatives, ensuring these can be straightforwardly integrated into real-world practice and embedded into long-term institutional strategies and/or policy frameworks.
- ➔ By promoting open access to project outputs and ensuring that materials are accessible and understandable for non-academic stakeholders, PERIFORMANCE will support equitable uptake and use of the generated knowledge. This approach strengthens transparency, broadens societal benefit, and enables diverse actors to apply the insights into practice.
- ➔ Deliver targeted training and capacity-building activities, alongside tailored learning materials and supporting resources, to empower stakeholder groups to adopt, adapt, and sustain meaningful engagement approaches beyond the project's duration.

In general terms, the project will support **meaningful transformations within cancer research and care ecosystems** and the **Mission implementation actions**, by:

- promoting and showcasing new innovative engaging activities;
- creating knowledge and reports for promoting trust in emerging technologies and data use;
- enabling a better landscape understanding - improving insight into the strengths, weaknesses, and opportunities across different territories- through the project reports;

- and via the repository of best practices, open tools, and “cookbooks” – with the capacity for adoption and adaptation in different contexts and scenarios-, contributing to systemic shifts toward more participatory, needs-driven research ecosystems.

TARGET GROUPS (“who?”)

PERIFORMANCE incorporates a broader spectrum of stakeholders by applying a **quadruple helix perspective on stakeholders**. This perspective compiles and get involved all the agents and collaborative ecosystems that PERIFORMANCE needs to create meaningful changes, perspectives and results. Specifically, the model involves 4 main interconnected sectors, which in general terms are: science, policy, industry, and society. For the project approach, the quadruple helix perspective has been readapted to recognise four major actors in the system covering a complete perspective of the CANCER whole chain, considering: cancer patients, survivors, and donors, and general public; research and healthcare professionals; industry partners in this area but also in the new technologies sector (AI, etc.); and policymakers, with special focus on local agents; all within the context of EU Mission Cancer.

In a deeper detail, the PERIFORMANCE's quadruple helix perspective includes:

A: CANCER PATIENTS, SURVIVORS, AND DONORS: Citizens-at-risk, patients and their representatives, including survivors and families, the BBMRI patient pillar forum, and the general public.

B: RESEARCH AND HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS: biobank managers, researchers, data scientists, clinicians, hospitals, universities.

C: INDUSTRY PARTNERS: industry professionals (biotech and pharma) but also AI developers, and IT specialists.

D: POLICYMAKERS: regulators, local and regional agents, thinktanks and accelerators, NGOs, innovators, and changemakers.

Figure 1. PERIFORMANCE's quadruple helix

This model was selected as it promotes dynamic interactions, knowledge sharing and shared responsibility, which are key to enable the ethical use of new technologies and to enhance the relevance and equity of public policies and research outcomes.

Additionally, it aims to co-create pioneering strategies through a research design that includes a wide range of perspectives, expertise, visions, needs, and expectations, offering valuable qualitative insights in this regard. Thus, this approach facilitates the identification of knowledge gaps and best practices, contributing to a more nuanced understanding of the complexities surrounding cancer and the variety of visions and needs.

This will enable synergistic optimisation of potential impact(s), leading to improved patient outcomes, broader societal benefits and meaningful health improvements, thus contributing to all EU Cancer Mission goals, directly or indirectly.

KEY MESSAGES (“what?”)

As **PERFORMANCE** is designed to understand and transform the **stakeholder engagement in cancer landscape** by addressing the ethical, legal, and societal implications (**ELSI**) of **cancer research and emerging technologies**, prior to define the specific messages to our target audiences, it is important firstly to define **our pillars**, as they complement our approach and focus on the definition of messages:

Mission: Cancer

Cancer is one of today’s greatest health challenges, driven by ageing populations, lifestyle factors, and environmental conditions.

The Horizon Europe Mission on Cancer, together with Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan, aims to improve lives through prevention, early diagnosis, treatment, and equitable access to care. Engaging all agents of the cancer value chain is key.

Biobanks: local gateways to global impact

As custodians of participants’ samples and data, biobank professionals can contribute to secure, effective use of resources, supporting innovation while safeguarding trust.

Biobanks are essential for cancer research, at the intersection between science and society, enabling and acting as data integration hubs. Also, as local actors have direct links to citizens, researchers, and healthcare providers to advance transdisciplinary research.

To this end, messages will be defined and tailored to each group in the quadruple helix based on these fundamental principles.

Emerging Technologies

Cancer research is increasingly data driven. Advances in AI, big data, and secure health data environments like the European Health Data Space (EHDS) are reshaping how we understand and treat cancer.

These technologies offer unprecedented opportunities but also raise ethical, legal, and societal challenges. Innovations must align with societal values and contributes to trust and equity.

Ethical, Legal, and Societal Implications (ELSI)

Integrating an ELSI perspective into cancer research ensures global trust, fairness, and respect for participants’ rights.

Embedding ELSI in technology development from an early stage is needed to ensure that progress benefits all, without compromising ethical standards or social equity.

CITIZENS, CANCER PATIENTS, SURVIVORS, AND DONORS:

Objectives

- To build trust and foster meaningful participation in biomedical advances and new technologies in cancer environment.
- To foster understanding of how artificial intelligence (AI), health data, biobanks, and emerging research infrastructures impact and improve cancer prevention, diagnosis, treatment, and care.
- To promote informed, autonomous participation in decision-making processes related to data, cancer research and new technologies with reliable, accessible, and actionable knowledge.
- To explain the ethical, legal, and societal implications (ELSI) of emerging technologies in cancer research in a transparent and understandable manner.

Key Messages

- **“Where science meets society to transform cancer research.”**
- It is fundamental that stakeholders contribute with insights, needs, priorities, expectations and interpretations of research emerging results and new technologies and innovations, ultimately generating more trust, context sensitive, and patients and practice-oriented approaches
- **“Science that responds, technology with purpose.”**
Demystifying AI and the European Health Data Space (EHDS) fears by explaining how these tools are used safely and ethically to improve cancer diagnosis and treatment, together with the supporting role of the biobanks.
Understanding research technologies empowers patients and citizens.
- **“Your data, shared ethically and securely, are key to accelerating cancer research”**
Learn how privacy is protected while enabling scientific progress.
- Raise awareness about data governance and the protection of societal rights in data use to promote and demand more transparent, ethical, and trustworthy data-driven practices.

Channels and Materials

- Accessible project website with interactive content (FAQs, explainers)
- Short informational capsules (video, webinars, animations and audiovisual material produced internally or using external resources)
- Easy-to-read leaflets and infographics
- Patient forums, co-creation workshops, and community dialogues
- Social media formats and articles adapted for non-technical audiences
- Introductory training modules and materials explaining core concepts in simple terms.
- Success stories narratives to humanise the project and demonstrate tangible impact.
- Open call campaign designed to be inclusive, transparent, and accessible to non-technical audiences, promoting the participation in collaboration with associations, researchers or local institutions.
- The cookbook will present step-by-step 'recipes' for engagement, participation or implementation, showing how participation has led to concrete benefits or changes, while enabling actionable exercises.

Collaborations with: EURORDIS - RARE DISEASES EUROPE, EPIONI, ELLOK and CANCER PATIENTS EUROPE networks, BBMRI's European Stakeholder Forum Patient Pillar, and additionally wider collaborations will be implemented with Spanish Cancer Patient Group (GEPAC), ECHOES project, local patient organisations, etc.

The communication strategy should incorporate specific attention to vulnerable audiences, including differences in age, gender, diverse abilities and socio-economic contexts, ensuring that all materials are understandable, accessible and culturally appropriate.

RESEARCH AND HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS:

Objectives

- To share evidence-based best practices and foster collaboration for the responsible, equitable, and ethical development and implementation of new cancer therapies, technologies, and research infrastructures.
- To promote participatory and inclusive research models that integrate societal perspectives from the outset.
- To support the uptake of PERIFORMANCE frameworks, methodologies, and tools within research practice.

Key Messages

- **“Sharing knowledge to advance in open and participatory cancer research.”**
- **“Develop, implement, and strengthen cancer research approaches guided by a responsible and ethical perspective”**
Share good practices and help strengthen responsible research and innovation.
- **“Cancer knowledge and research advancements must be developed and implemented within a robust ethical and technical framework.”**
Researchers must consider ensuring transparency, equity, and awareness of biases and under-represented populations, particularly in the use of AI, EHDS, and research infrastructures.

Channels and Materials

- Social media (LinkedIn, BlueSky) contents adapted for specialised audiences
- Leaflets, infographics and website to raise awareness of the project’s relevance, tools, and opportunities.
- Technical webinars and expert roundtables, forums, co-creation workshops, and community dialogues
- Video will visually demonstrate real-world use cases and workflows, helping professionals grasp the value research integration and inclusivity.
- Scientific conferences (posters, oral presentations)
- Peer-reviewed open-access publications
- “Open Resources” section on the project website (guidelines, toolkits, datasets)
- Success stories showcasing concrete examples of impact and best practices, building trust and motivating researchers.
- Open calls campaign to actively invite researchers and healthcare professionals to participate.
- Cookbook will provide practical, step-by-step guidance translating research outputs into implementable practices for healthcare and biobanking professionals.
- Public deliverables (including those published on CORDIS) openly available to act as references and guidance for applicability, ensuring the long-term visibility and sustainability of project results within the European research and biobanking ecosystem.

Collaborations with: cancer-related projects funded by Horizon Europe (Mission: Cancer calls) and EU4Health (cancer projects tool), BBMRI national nodes, EU-AMRI partners, etc.

Specifically, for Biobanking networks and research infrastructures:

Objectives

- To strengthen the role of biobank networks as key enablers of ethical, participatory, and high-quality cancer research, enhancing trust among participants, patients, researchers, and society by promoting transparency and accountability in biobanking.
- To support biobank networks in aligning their practices with emerging European frameworks, including the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and AI regulation.
- To facilitate the uptake of PERIFORMANCE tools, guidelines, and best practices within biobank governance, access procedures, and engagement strategies.

Key Messages

- **“Biobanks are reliable infrastructures that guarantee ethical, compliant data sharing for AI development and integration into the EHDS.”**
Ethical governance and stakeholder engagement are central to sustainable biobanking.
- **“Responsible data sharing enables better cancer research.”**
“PERIFORMANCE supports biobanks in operationalising ethics-by-design, by sharing practical tools and frameworks to help translate ELSI principles into daily biobank practice.
- **“Participation improves governance.”**
Engaging donors, patients, and communities enhances fairness, transparency, and long-term impact.

Channels and Materials

- Targeted calls with a biobank focus, to facilitate and highlight innovative engagement initiatives
- Guidelines, toolkits and case studies showcasing good practices in participatory biobanking
- Contributions to biobank network meetings (e.g. BBMRI-ERIC events, national node assemblies)

INDUSTRY PARTNERS (Technological and Pharmaceutical):

Objectives

- To highlight opportunities for innovation and public-private collaborations in the responsible, equitable, and ethical development of cancer technologies and therapies.
- To demonstrate the strategic value of responsible research and innovation (RRI) and ELSI integration in the innovation and development process.
- To strengthen the link between technological innovation, trust, and societal impact.
- To showcase collaborative best practices that align innovation with public values, promoting patient-centred approaches.

Key Messages

- **“Ethical health data governance is the next frontier of innovation.”**
Integrating ELSI principles builds trust and enables sustainable innovation furthering holistic progress.
- **“Good practices in data use and stakeholder engagement are drivers of competitive and socially aligned innovation.”**
These ELSI and RRI practices promote greater awareness and knowledge, and encourage more informed, and therefore more aware and active citizen and stakeholders’ participation, contributing and promoting social innovations in cancer research, diagnosis, treatment, and care.

Channels and Materials

- LinkedIn for professional networks
- Digital and print flyers, videos and websites that enable industry actors to explore concrete opportunities for uptake and promote innovation potential and collaboration opportunities.
- Participation in technical webinars, forums, co-creation workshops and community dialogues gives the sector a voice. Targeted workshops on ELSI-by-design and responsible AI development are promoted.
- Case studies showcasing successful collaborative models and the promotion of the cookbook with recommendations derived from project results will support replication, uptake, and scaling by relevant stakeholders.
- Public deliverables (including publication on CORDIS) aspire to promote industry engagement in responsible technology development and transfer, including social innovation.

Collaborations with: EuropaBio, National industry associations such as Spanish Biotechnology association (ASEBIO), FENIN (Spanish Federation of Healthcare Technology Companies), Spanish Association for Responsible Artificial Intelligence (AEINAR); Ellis Foundation - European Laboratory for Learning and Intelligent Systems; etc.

POLICY MAKERS, LOCAL AGENTS AND REGULATORS

Objectives

- To position PERIFORMANCE and its outputs as a **reference model of good practice** in ethical governance, sustainability, stakeholder engagement, and visibility under Horizon Europe.
- To provide a full view of the research environment that will benefit from more inclusive policies, integrating the perspective of all interested parties.
- To demonstrate that Cancer Mission objectives are best achieved through active societal participation in the design of research infrastructures and emerging technologies.
- To support the transfer of project results into actionable, adapted-to-context recommendations and initiatives at EU, national, and regional levels.

Key Messages

- **“Connecting excellence: participation drives progress.”**
Data and evidence should guide decisions that affect the health of all citizens. Trust and transparency are key values to guide this progress.
- **“Inclusive and participatory research leads to more effective and trusted public policies.”**
PERIFORMANCE provides evidence and practical recommendations to support EHDS implementation and AI regulation in oncology, aligned with the EU Cancer Mission.

Channels and Materials

- Digital/print flyer, video and website to local and government actors to understand the relevance of promoting innovative engagement processes and actions on potential cancer understanding and research development.
- Posts on social media accounts will foster visibility and dialogue.
- Press media and non-scientific articles with narratives that support informed decision-making and public-sector uptake.

- Participation in technical webinars, forums, co-creation workshops and community dialogues to raise the debate, positioning project results within ongoing policy, regulatory, and standardisation discussions.
- Webinars and training materials to build capacities for developing best practices in local contexts.
- Case studies showcasing successful collaborative models help to illustrate real-world policy impact, supporting evidence-based policy development and implementation.
- Open calls campaign to actively invite agents to promote in long term these actions.
- Promotion of the cookbook and recommendations derived from project deliverables and case studies to facilitate the adoption of best practices across research, healthcare, industry, and biobanking ecosystems, enabling evidence-based policies.
- Joint events and cross-project collaborations within the Cancer Mission to enforce relevance of these initiatives.
- Open repositories ensuring sustainability and reuse of outputs

Collaborations with: Innpulso Network- Support for local innovation: Promotion by local entities; national council for Science, Technology and Innovation Policy; ECHOES stakeholder groups, National Mirror Group Cancer Mission, etc.

COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION MATERIALS AND TOOLS - METHODS (“HOW?”)

A set of communication materials will be developed to be used by all partners ensuring strong and consistent presentation of the project to stakeholders and interested parties (brochures, presentation video, etc.). A unified project image and common design guidelines have been created to accompany the strategy. These elements feature a more attractive, modern, and engaging visual identity, helping to consolidate the project’s visibility and enhance stakeholder interest across communication channels. The following section explains the materials that will be used in the project.

1. Initial set of communication tools

Project logo and common design guidelines: The logo development followed the discussions with the consortium to highlight through simple elements the following values:

- *Public engagement:* participation, inclusion, community;
- *Research infrastructures and technology:* science, data, networks, technology, IA, EHDS, innovation, connections, complex systems;
- *Mission Cancer:* oncology, precision medicine, understanding of cancer through stakeholder engagement, patients and families; common mission.

The logo is based on a typographic style with graphic accents for including cancer concept; and visual elements that represent intersection between technology, research, ELSI and society, covering patient centricity and proximity.

In line with this, the following materials have been created:

- Basic graphic guidelines (definition of icon style, shapes, and simple visual resources).
- Selection of primary and secondary typography (digital and editorial use).
- Primary and secondary colour palette.

- Basic visual guide
- Design of base templates: presentations or internal documents, headers, and signatures

Figure 2. Elements and colours of the logo

Project brochures: The leaflet will be used for general communication, publicity and promotional purposes in meetings, conferences, workshops and other dissemination events. It will be used as a "business card" of the project, its first introduction and presentation. It will provide a brief description of the project, a summary of its objectives, as well as the institutions that make up the consortium, and will include the website address and social networks.

2. Project Website and Social Media

The PERIFORMANCE website is the main hub for all online project communications. The project website will be the project's main channel of information, where all content related to and/or generated by the project is to be uploaded: events, materials, publications, guides, results, etc. Since it will host all project outputs, knowledge and news, all promotional work should -where applicable - link to the website. The website is divided, according to the defined structure, in the following pages:

- HOME
- THE PROJECT
- THE TEAM
- RESULTS AND RESOURCES
- NEWS
- CONTACT

With the following subsections:

Home

The Project

- Context
- Objectives
- Work packages (WP)
- Our stakeholders
- Related projects

The team

Results and resources

- Milestones & Deliverables
- Results: Cookbook / Publications / Tools / Study cases

News

Contact

*Not all the sections will be active in the website launch, but they will be incorporated as soon as the project advances or the content is created (ex. press releases, publications, etc.).

The current domain from which its content can be viewed is <https://periformance.com>, but it will be moved and active at <https://periformance.eu/>

The website hosts validated project content and consolidated messages to avoid fragmentation and to maintain consistency across channels. It will be divided based on the previous intuitive menu to improve findability and will show the project's logo, the EU emblem, contact details, social media platforms, newsletter subscription (when available), logos from all institutions that make up the consortium, and relevant documents and reports (e.g., Zenodo for open outputs) will be shared.

Additionally, accessibility factors will be implemented as fundamental part of the project spirit, broadening audience reach and inclusivity. Besides, several factors regarding compliance, privacy, and security will be executed (GDPR compliant cookie consent and privacy notices; clear data processing purposes; opt in newsletter forms consent; secure hosting, etc.).

Social Networks

The project's social media channels have been designed to enhance visibility and act as a powerful amplification engine. They will distribute relevant content, ideas, and debates to broader audiences, fostering new forms of communication with key stakeholders—particularly patients, cancer ecosystem actors, industry representatives, policymakers, and citizen communities. These channels will help us to measure the real-world impact of the project's messages. The PERIFORMANCE social network will embrace:

- 1) **LinkedIn:** <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-periformance-project/>

It will serve as platform for discussion, interaction, collection of information, and communication of the project

outputs to experts (from research, industries, SMEs, NGOs, local authorities, etc.). LinkedIn will serve as an effective tool to assist us in building a network of organizations and people who are interested in participating in project activities.

- 2) **Bluesky** (instead of X/Twitter). In the proposal, it was defined X as a complementary social network to inform the broader community about both technical and less technical information. Nevertheless, in an internal project meeting, it was decided to move to more alienated European values channel, and therefore a mirror profile was created in Bluesky: [@euperiformance.bsky.social](https://bsky.app/profile/euperiformance.bsky.social). The X EU PERIFORMANCE project account will be maintained for some time: [EU PERIFORMANCE project \(@EU_Performance\) / X](https://twitter.com/EU_Performance).

- 3) **Facebook** and **Instagram** (IG) accounts are going to be created to connect with patients' organisations, as they are key channels used among these profiles. IG will be launched in the following months.

[EU Periformance project](https://www.periformance.eu/)

These channels will serve as platform for discussion, interaction, collection of information, and communication of the project outputs, to experts (from research, industries, SMEs, NGOs, local authorities, etc.).

All partners will be encouraged to create relevant content for the social media channels, although pertinent content can be posted and shared directly through their channels.

Once the DEC is operational, a social media communications calendar will be scheduled. The key areas into which the content will be categorised align with the Cancer Mission, ELSI, stakeholder engagement and co-creation focus of the project. These areas are divided into:

- **PROJECT: PERIFORMANCE content:**
 - o General awareness (what is PERIFORMANCE; mission, vision, values; why stakeholder engagement matters in cancer research; our pillars; etc.)
 - o Project progress, events & community (key moments; upcoming events and calls to participate, workshops, deliverables submitted or milestones reached; launch of tools, reports, or resources; participation in events and conferences, etc.)
- **TEAM: Consortium partners:** Who is behind the project and their expertise (Partner file: roles and expertise within the consortium; quotes from partners on why PERIFORMANCE matters)
- **INITIATIVES: Cancer Mission, policy context & stakeholder engagement:** Relevant external content associated to main PERIFORMANCE objectives highlighted within our channels (Voices from patients, citizens, and professionals; EU reports; peer-reviewed publications regarding EHDS, AI Act, and cancer research governance; Ethical, legal, and societal dimensions of research; etc.)
- **COMMUNITY: Biobanks & Research Infrastructures, and others:** role of infrastructures in ethical cancer research (case study highlights; best practices insights on engagement).
- **KEY dates:** important events related to the topics covered in the project (World Cancer Day, Women and science; etc.)

To increase consistency and analytics, some optional “Content Tags” can be used:

- #CancerMission
- #StakeholderEngagement
- #ELSI
- #ResponsibleAI
- #HealthData
- #Biobanks
- #Participation
- #PublicEngagement,
- #Innovation
- #Science&society
- #EHDS
- #Artificialintelligence

These channels and diverse contents aim to humanise the project and create touchpoints with diverse audiences.

A structured content calendar will be established to plan and coordinate all publications. On average, 4 pieces of content will be produced each month across the different social media channels (the number will be increased when necessary for updates and urgent notices). The publication schedule will remain flexible, as the launch of each piece will depend on its relevance, urgency, and overall context.

Monthly Content Calendar

Figure 3. Content calendar for social networks.

3. Other engaging activities:

Newsletters

The newsletter is expected to be published and shared quarterly. This digital publication, which will be written in English, will collect articles of interest about the project, its results and activities. The function of the newsletter is two-fold:

- To disseminate the contents of the project with the view to increase and create the awareness around the project.
- To retain users' loyalty through useful content, thus improving their engagement with the project.

The elaboration and diffusion tool of choice will be Mailchimp. A link for subscription and all newsletters will be available on the project's website. We will use the Mailchimp platform formats to include all the functionalities required for an effective newsletter, such as personalized headlines and footers, and to offer clear and accessible links to be able to unsubscribe.

Video and webinars

A video for presenting the project will be launched in the first year of the project, which will serve as a powerful, communication material to increase awareness, and to define and communicate in a simple and effective way complex ideas developed within the project. In addition, the video will be adapted into several short clips to be shared across social media channels, extending its reach and impact.

Additionally, throughout the project's lifetime, a series of webinars will be held to support the fulfilment of the project's aims and the Work Package (WP) objectives. These webinars will explain the project methodologies and ways of engagement, promote participation and collaboration, and present key aspects of the project as well as recommendations and ethical solutions derived from the consortium's research. They will also present

case studies and best practices and share training materials. These webinars will be recorded and uploaded to YouTube, as well as being shared on the project website and social media pages.

Press Media and Non-Scientific Articles

These materials aim to raise public awareness and enhance the visibility of PERIFORMANCE beyond academic and professional audiences. Press releases, media articles, and non-scientific publications translate complex research topics—such as stakeholder engagement, AI, health data, and ELSI—into accessible narratives, fostering understanding, trust, and societal interest in the project and its objectives.

It will require collaboration with magazines, review and coordination by the consortium and, where appropriate, expert profiles. The content generated for magazines will be used for social media posts, news and blog articles on the website, newsletters where appropriate, etc. For this type of publication, it would be interesting to identify:

- Opinion leaders and references in the area
- Corporative content of relevance
- Own or external experiences and success stories

A project launch press release has been shared with all partners to facilitate dissemination through their own websites and communication channels, thereby broadening our reach and increasing awareness of the project across trusted and established networks from the consortium.

4. Network building and exploitation

The creation and strengthening of relationships with stakeholders are key elements in the dissemination and exploitation of the PERIFORMANCE project. Network building will be undertaken by all the consortium members along the project to access and build links with the different PERIFORMANCE quadruple helix stakeholders, involving patients and associations, R&I institutions, industry associations, other projects and key policymakers' entities, among others. The identified networks, organizations, communities and individuals will continuously be informed and updated about on-going work, through direct and personalized contact and relations.

To this extent, several consulting groups for the project will be created to build and reflect perceptions, needs, strengths, limitations and key initiatives within the different WPs. Networking, which will have European, international, national and local contexts dimensions, will be developed by the members of the Consortium, and would be based on the following activities:

- Drawing up a list of all relevant stakeholders and target groups, at local, regional, national and European levels, who could be involved in both general and/or more tailored and specific input.
- Identifying and selecting relevant actors and initiatives that can be contacted, actively involved in, or support the PERIFORMANCE activities to develop case studies and other materials.

In this sense, several **workshops, focus groups, and interviews** will take place to shape this network building within the project. These participatory formats are core methodological tools for PERIFORMANCE. They facilitate two-way dialogue, enabling stakeholders to share experiences, identify gaps, and co-develop solutions.

They also ensure that project outputs are grounded in real needs, diverse perspectives, and lived experiences, enhancing relevance and legitimacy.

Within the WPs implementations, the following workshops/focus groups must be created:

- **WP1: Identification of Stakeholder Engagement Practices:** diverse range of stakeholders in Belgium, Austria, Spain, Latvia, and Estonia will be invited, aiming for approximately 10 participants per country, with the aim of identifying gaps and context-specific needs to support the development of guidelines, training activities, and pilot engagement practices. It will also help to capture real-world experiences and challenges.
- **WP3: Social and Ethical Analysis of Public Engagement: With and for Health Data Spaces and Artificial Intelligence:** ~50 stakeholders in contact with health data (max. 10 people from the following countries: Austria, Belgium, France, Latvia, Spain, some also from WP1). The aim will be to understand and evaluate societal and ethical implications of AI & EHDS in stakeholder interactions and the use in cancer research & biobanking. Covering the exploration of emerging technologies in public engagement and dissemination (e.g., chatbots) as well.
- **WP5: Embedded reflection on the contribution of the project to Mission: Cancer goals.** Two workshops will be held with diverse stakeholders to co-create engagement strategies and discuss the Mission: Cancer goals, ensuring a multidisciplinary approach in the development of a comprehensive set of best practices for stakeholder engagement.

The WP6 will be supporting the purpose of these workshops by promoting its announcement, facilitating registration in case it is required, supporting during the celebration with materials and technical support if needed, and sharing main conclusions and learnings in support to the WP leaders.

Participation within the context of major events and organisation of workshops demonstrating the project's major achievements and presenting results will also be promoted within the WP6 coordinating visibility actions.

A dedicated form for stakeholders interested in participating in the project will be created on the website and widely promoted through social networks, events, and workshops. This will open up new ways of engaging with profiles outside of the consortium's existing networks that have a direct interest in being actively involved in our activities. These profiles include patient organisations, healthcare professionals, regional authorities, civil society groups, industry partners and research infrastructures.

Connection with other EU projects and networks

In close collaboration with the ECHOS EU and canSERV projects, and leveraging the [Cancer Projects Tool](#), we aim to actively foster participation and engagement within the PERIFORMANCE consortium and across related initiatives. This will be supported through regular joint meetings with the leaders of these consortia, where we will exchange updates, coordinate activities, and ensure strategic alignment.

Open Call Campaign

An open call for specific bottom-up engagement exercises in diverse contexts, particularly biobanking, focusing mainly on cancer research, will be launched at the beginning of the project (around M 6-10), ensuring that the unique needs of local contexts and stakeholders are met.

The open call is designed to broaden participation beyond the consortium by inviting external stakeholders—such as patient organisations, researchers, biobanks, and civil society actors, such as universities and schools—

to contribute experiences, case studies, or initiatives. Open call campaigns promote inclusiveness, transparency, and diversity of perspectives, reinforcing PERIFORMANCE's commitment to participatory research and co-creation fostering collaborative and ethically grounded cancer research, paying attention to biobanks' role in the field and to ethical innovation, and interoperability with emerging health data frameworks and technologies. A broad visibility is expected, mobilising within consortium networks, and with external agents related with our target audiences (European School Net, University4all, Spanish National Biobanks networks, BBMRI National Nodes, researchers' networks, European patient organisations, associated NGOs, own institutions communication departments, etc.).

Success Stories

Success stories showcase concrete examples of positive change generated by PERIFORMANCE or by related initiatives, inspiring new ideas that can be adapted to different contexts and geographies. They help bring experiences closer to diverse audiences and foster collaborations among entities within the same country or internationally. These stories also encourage the uptake of successful models tested in other institutions, broadening and amplifying their impact. Examples may include effective engagement practices, policy actions that incorporate the needs of vulnerable populations, meaningful cocreation and participation initiatives in cancer research, or the adoption of exemplary practices related to engaging new actors, for example, demonstrating the societal value of biobanks-enabled cancer research.

By showcasing real-world impact and lessons learned, these stories demonstrate the value of co-creation and responsible innovation in cancer research, which we aim they help to inspire replication and uptake. These series of success stories, incorporating multi-dimensional perspectives, will be published on the website and social media.

Public Deliverables

Public deliverables comprise reports, guidelines, methodological frameworks, and enhanced strategies that will be openly accessible through the project website and EU platforms. These outputs aim to ensure transparency, accountability, and equitable access to project results, enabling their dissemination, reuse, and long-term exploitation by researchers, policymakers, healthcare systems, industry, and civil-society stakeholders. In addition, platforms such as **OPENAIRE**, **ResearchGate** and **Zenodo** will be used to disseminate publications and project outputs with persistent, citable identifiers, facilitating visibility, traceability, and uptake across the research ecosystem.

Cookbook and Training Materials

The PERIFORMANCE **Cookbook** and its associated training materials seek to transform project findings into practical, step-by-step guidance for implementing ethical, inclusive, and co-creative stakeholder engagement in cancer research. These resources will strengthen capacities across institutions by offering concrete tools, examples, and adaptable approaches. They will support long-term exploitation by enabling organisations to integrate PERIFORMANCE methodologies, best practices, and engagement models into their own workflows and local contexts.

These materials will be shared through the same channels used for project deliverables—including the website, EU platforms, and open repositories—and further amplified through dedicated sections in our social networks, newsletters, and communication campaigns.

Others:

Horizon Europe Rules

Following articles 17.2 and 17.3 from GRANT AGREEMENT 101216808, all project partners must implement the communication and EU visibility commitments, ensuring that any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) as well as equipment and major results funded by the grant include:

- EU emblem.
- And, when appropriate, the following text:
 - “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

MATERIAL QUALITY CRITERIA

All materials, content and actions arising from the PERIFORMANCE project must comply with the following criteria of quality, accessibility and regulatory consistency:

- Design of materials in line with the visual identity created: logo, fonts, templates and consistent graphic style.
- Clarity and accessibility in the messages and materials disseminated, ensuring the use of clear and easy-to-read language and full digital accessibility.
- Inclusion and gender perspective, promoting equal and non-discriminatory communication that reflects the social and scientific diversity of the project.
- Adaptation to the different stakeholders identified in the so-called quadruple helix (citizens/patients, research community, industry and policy makers), using messages, formats and channels appropriate for each group.
- Compliance with Open Science and Open Access policies, in line with European Commission guidelines.
- Consistency, complementarity and proper exploitation of project results, through coordination of work with the consortium's other work packages.
- Consistency with European regulations on the visibility of projects funded under Horizon Europe, ensuring the correct use of European Union emblems, references and graphic elements.

Table 1 provides a brief overview of the materials regarding target stakeholders, in line with the content and scope. It also includes associated indicators to measure and track the expected impacts and effective reach.

Table 1. Description of C&D materials associated with the focus target groups and indicators

Channels	Target groups*				KPIs for project duration	
	PATIENTS	RESEARCH	INDUSTRY	GOVERNMENT		
Digital/print flyer	x	x	x	x	No. Flyers	100 + digital version downloads (+100)
Video + short clips	x	x	x	x	No. Views	500
Website	x	x	x	x	No. Visitors/News Newsletter subscriptions Report downloads Collaboration requests	1000/10 +100 +100 +5
Posts on social media accounts	x	x	x	x	No. Followers/Posts Engagement rate (likes + comments + shares) Reposts by institutions	500/400 5 positive Interactions in posts
Press media, non-scientific articles	x			x	No. Articles	10
Participation in European and international events ^[1]		x	x	x	No. of Events	10
Webinars & Training materials	x	x	x	x	No. of Attendees / views	120 /500
Success stories	x	x	x	x	No. success stories	10
Open calls campaign	x	x		x	No. presented proposals	50
Workshops, focus groups, and interviews	x	x	x	x	No. participants	50-100
Cookbook	x	x	x	x	No. downloads	+150

Public deliverables (incl. publication on CORDIS)		x	x	x	No. Deliverables	12
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* A: CANCER PATIENTS, SURVIVORS, AND DONORS

B: RESEARCH AND HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS

C: INDUSTRY AND PRIVATE FOUNDATIONS

D: POLICY- AND DECISION-MAKERS AT NATIONAL AND EUROPEAN LEVELS

MEASURING IMPACT - METHODS (“HOW WELL?”)

To strengthen the evaluation of our dissemination and communication strategy, we will implement a comprehensive assessment framework. This framework will measure not only the outreach and engagement levels of the project’s main communication channels but also their effectiveness in driving meaningful impact aligned with the project’s outcomes and its impact in Cancer mission. Our evaluation will adopt a quadruple helix perspective, ensuring that our strategy reaches and benefits patients and donors, research and healthcare professionals, industry partners, and policymakers.

Table 2. Evaluation Framework for Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Dissemination channel	Objective	Measurable content	Measures	KPIs for project duration	Impact verification	Target groups
Digital/print flyer	Strong and consistent presentation of the project	1 brochure adapted for different profiles QR redirecting to website	Track the number of physical and digital brochures distributed	100 printed +100 digital downloads Increased number of website visitors associated to brochures use and distribution	Viewer retention rates and materials distributed will be analysed to assess whether content is effectively capturing audience interest and engagement with project themes.	Patients Research Industry Government
Presentation video	Strengthened project visibility and stakeholder familiarity	1 video + short clips across social media channels	Track the number of video views tracked	500 views (YouTube, website) Increased engagement	No. viewers, to assess whether content is effectively capturing	Patients Research Industry Government

				in social networks (new subscribers and reactions)	audience interest. Produce social media content associated with the video to monitor its impact, audience understanding, level of interest, and overall engagement.	
Website	Strong and consistent presentation of the project Improved accessibility to project information	1 website	Number of visits per time period Presence in partners' websites	+300 visits per year (+ 1.000 for the whole project)	Regular review of website analytics to help identify high-traffic content and areas requiring optimization. Regularly update content to keep stakeholders informed and engaged. Identify content that can redirect audiences to the website and encourage the adoption of similar approaches	Patients Research Industry Government

Social media accounts (LinkedIn, Bluesky + Ig + Fb).	Dissemination of project outcomes Broad audience engagement and knowledge transfer	1 publication a month	Monitor engagement rate (likes, comments, shares of posts)	Network community of around 500 followers Visits to the website and related materials	If engagement is low despite high follower numbers, content strategies will be adjusted and partner institutions and stakeholders will be encouraged to amplify dissemination, enabling timely adjustments to the project's communication strategy	Patients Research Industry Government
Press media, non-scientific articles	Increased outreach and engagement	Articles published in non-scientific media at key moments of the project lifetime	Number of publications and media appearances	+ 10 appearances in media (media coverage)	Greater public awareness and policy influence	Patients Government
Participation in events & joint actions with other EU/internat. projects	Visibility in scientific and policy circles Improved collaboration and networking	Conference presentations, panel discussions, networking events	Number of events featuring the project by different channels (posters, presentations, meetings, flyers, etc.)	10 events assisted within the consortium	Strengthened synergies and cross-project learning Enhanced credibility and dissemination of project outcomes in expert communities	Research Industry Government

<p>Webinars (recording on YouTube, shared on website and social media pages).</p>	<p>Dissemination of project outcomes Stakeholder education and best practices dissemination</p>	<p>4 webinars</p>	<p>Track the number of attendees per event from different stakeholder groups Measure participant interaction during webinars (e.g., questions asked). Assess knowledge gained through post-event feedback surveys</p>	<p>120 attendees +500 views of the videos (<i>all of them</i>) Survey feedback</p>	<p>If attendance numbers are high but engagement levels are low (e.g., limited interaction), adjustments will be made to event formats (e.g., more interactive Q&A sessions)</p>	<p>Patients Research Industry Government</p>
<p>Success stories</p>	<p>Increased public recognition and cross-sector engagement</p>	<p>1 publication every 6 months; Deliverables, website and social media content (LinkedIn, Bluesky)</p>	<p>Track the number of website visits & unique downloads of success stories Track average time spent on success stories page</p>	<p>10-15 detected key stories for communication materials development</p>	<p>Leverage LinkedIn, Bluesky, ResearchGate, and other platforms for dissemination. Encourage partners and stakeholders to share success stories.</p>	<p>Patients Research Industry Government</p>

					Monitor re-sharing and mentions in other websites or publications	
Open calls campaign	Broad audience engagement and knowledge transfer	Website and social media campaigns Collaboration with relevant platforms, partners and EU initiatives and infrastructures	Number of participants in open calls	More than 50 proposals, coming from different countries representing EU key areas 15 projects, reaching 100+ people	Leverage LinkedIn, Bluesky, BBMRI, and other platforms for campaign dissemination; encouraging partners and stakeholders to participate and spread the call among different stakeholders creating multidisciplinary consortiums and perspectives	Patients Research Industry Government
Cookbook and training materials	Facilitation of best practice implementation	Interactive content, training modules	Number of downloads, registrations, and follow-up requests	+150-300 downloads New collaborations established Patient organizations, Policy and industry engagement	Strengthened visibility and implementation among different actors and stakeholders and cross-project learning and synergies Enhanced knowledge and creation	Patients Research Industry Government

					of expert communities and success stories	
Workshops, focus groups, and interviews	Deeper insights into stakeholder needs and collaborative innovation	5 focus group discussions, 5 Semi-structured interviews	Number of attendees Number of contacts generated (requests for information, registrations, leads)	50-100 List with invited participants with presence of quadrupole helix profiles (Multidisciplinary participation of the profiles in the working groups)	If engagement is low despite high efforts to reach different profiles, partner institutions and stakeholders will be encouraged to amplify dissemination and define key profiles to be mobilised to participate	Patients Research Industry Government
Public deliverables	Dissemination and visibility of project main outputs, sharing new knowledge, practices and recommendations	12 deliverables	Number of deliverables shared on open-access repositories (e.g., Zenodo, ResearchGate, EU project portals)	12	Regular verification of number of downloads of deliverables and citations/references in academic papers, reports, or policy briefs.	Research Industry Government

An enhanced Stakeholder Engagement Metrics Table is being developed to complement the indicators with impact assessment:

Table 3. Impact assessment of Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder Engagement Approach	KPIs	Impact Assessment
Direct outreach initiatives (meetings, co-creation workshops)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 5 focus group discussions (WP1) - 5 semi-structured interviews and focus groups with key stakeholders (WP3) - Informational webinars and Q&A sessions for proposals development (WP4) - Open call - 2 embedded reflection sessions—both online and in-person—multistakeholder workshops (WP5) - 4 thematic webinars using a “train the trainer” approach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement metrics: Number of active participants, follow-up collaborations established - Diversity & Inclusion: Track the number of attendees from different stakeholder groups, including underrepresented groups - Impact on decision-making: recommendations and possible changes identified to be implemented in stakeholder practices or policies as a result of participation
Surveys and feedback mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ongoing surveys and feedback collection - Sentiment analysis of qualitative feedback 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement quality: Response rate, qualitative feedback on engagement quality - Learning impact: Increase in knowledge after project participation or use of associated materials - Continuous improvement: Adjustments made based on feedback trends
Long-term stakeholder involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continuous engagement programs (mentorship, ambassador roles, collaboration forums) - Stakeholder contributions to project outputs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustained engagement: Number of sustained interactions, repeat engagement rates - Co-creation success: Stakeholder-led initiatives emerging in the project
Community building & networking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of participants in stakeholder networking events - Online engagement in project forums or discussion groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Network expansion: Increase in cross-sector stakeholder collaborations - Multidisciplinary community-driven initiatives

In terms of training (**WP6**), we expect approximately 40 participants for each of the four webinars, resulting in a total of 160 participants. Additionally, around 20 participants are anticipated for the “train the trainer” online sessions. It is envisaged that each trainee could further train at least 10 more individuals, significantly expanding the project’s impact over time. The “train the trainers” approach equips local and regional stakeholders with the tools and knowledge to implement effective engagement strategies, fostering community capacity building.

Lastly, participants across all WPs will participate in outreach activities such as scientific publications and conference participations to disseminate the results.

COMMUNICATION TEAM - METHODS (“WITH WHO?”)

A Communication Team will be established within the consortium to work in the communication, exploitation and dissemination strategy, ensuring that project messages, materials and approaches are accurate, relevant, consistent and aligned with project objectives and stakeholder needs. Engagement and internal coordination will be structured and continuous through the following working methods:

- **Periodic coordination meetings**, to plan, align, and monitor communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, including timelines, responsibilities, and key milestones. During the meeting, the Communication Team will regularly review internal feedback and performance indicators to refine communication strategies and adapt actions throughout the project lifecycle.
- **Internal content co-creation**: Consortium partners will actively contribute to the development, edition and approval of communication materials, ensuring accuracy and language appropriateness. The Communication Team will establish internal procedures for drafting, reviewing, validating, and approving communication outputs, ensuring compliance with project objectives, ethical standards, and EU visibility requirements.
- **Support in the exploitation and uptake of project outputs**: Internal discussions will ensure that communication actions support exploitation pathways, uptake of results, and long-term sustainability, linking dissemination activities with associated networks and actors within the consortium that could be interested in project results use and implementation.
- **Key date and milestone coordination**: The team will maintain a shared communication calendar highlighting project milestones, deliverable releases, events, open calls, and policy-relevant moments to ensure timely and coordinated outreach.

Each Consortium member has appointed one or two communication officers within their team. These officers will coordinate with the Work Package (WP) leader and report any relevant communication activity occurring within their work or networks. They will also bring national-level initiatives that can be shared and highlighted within the project to enhance visibility, foster alignment, and promote best-practice exchange. A 'DEC' folder will act as an online repository for sharing project templates and approved corporate content, uploading relevant articles and sharing related content of interest.

The Communication group is composed by the following entities:

Table 4. COMMUNICATION BOARD MEMBERS

BIOBANKS AND BIOMOLECULAR RESOURCES RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE CONSORTIUM (BBMRI-ERIC) – Coordinator
FUNDACION SECTOR PUBLICO ESTATAL CENTRO NACIONAL INVESTIGACIONES ONCOLOGICAS CARLOS III -FSP CNIO Co-coordinator of Communication, exploitation and dissemination
LATVIJAS UNIVERSITATE – Coordination of training
CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DE RECHERCHE SUR LE CANCER

UNIVERSITAT WIEN
UNIVERSITA TA MALTA
KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN
TARTU ULIKOOL
STICHTING HET NEDERLANDS KANKER INSTITUUT-ANTONI VAN LEEUWENHOEK ZIEKENHUIS
EURORDIS - RARE DISEASES EUROPE
ELLINIKO DIKTYO FRONTISTON EPIONI
ELLINIKI OMOSPONDIA KARKINOU ELL OK
CANCER PATIENTS EUROPE

C, D & E PLAN: INTERNAL GUIDELINES

From an internal work perspective, the following guideline aims to guarantee the correct development and application of this Plan:

- The Plan will be reviewed every 12 months to monitor progress and results, as well as to provide revision or modification, accordingly, depending on the development of the project. Findings and suggested modifications will be part of the Periodic Reporting.
- The WP6 leader will coordinate all actions, ensure the project members provide the necessary content and monitor evaluation through the communication, dissemination and exploitation matrix. This responsibility lies with FSP CNIO.

ACTIVITIES FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF THE COMMUNICATION PLAN - TIME (“WHEN?”)

The DEC strategy will be carried out in accordance with the following indicative schedule:

Phases	Duration (months)	Description of main activities and deliverables
Phase 1 - Strategic planning, identity and launch	M1-M6	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Preparation and approval of the Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan, with objectives, audiences, channels, timetable and KPIs.- Development of the basic project website (news, partners, events, results, open resources) following the project's visual identity guidelines (logo, fonts).- Creation of social media profiles (LinkedIn, X/BlueSky, Instagram, Facebook).
Phase 2 - Dissemination and initial training Disseminate preliminary results.	M7-M18	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Production of the initial presentation video.- Generation of content and campaigns on social media- Organisation of webinars, workshops and online training sessions.- Preparation of initial training and communication materials (graphics, audiovisuals, digital).- Development of newsletters for selected profiles.- Updating and maintenance of the basic website.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Participation and visibility at scientific conferences and events.
Phase 3 – Enhancing visibility and impact Strengthening communication of pilot cases and interim results	M19–M30	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Preparation of training and communication materials (graphics, audiovisuals, digital).- Development of an advanced website with interactive content included in the basic website.- Participation and visibility at scientific conferences and events.- Organisation of webinars, workshops and online training sessions.- Updating and publication of the interactive Cookbook of best practice. ➔ Consolidation of best practices and embedded reflections
Phase 4 – Closure and sustainability	M31–M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Project closure activities.- Production of audiovisual materials to disseminate results.- Consolidation of the impact achieved and evaluation of visibility and participation indicators in summaries and newsletter- Support for the final event to present the results.- Sustainability of the website and the digital resources generated.- Strategic dissemination of the results and experiences generated within the scope of the project with key entities.

These activities will be coordinated with main dates within the project: open call launch, open workshops, attended events, etc.

COMMITMENT TO OPEN SCIENCE PRINCIPLES

The results of the project's research will be published in prestigious and specialized scientific journals and publications for their wider dissemination, repercussion and impact, in order to favour that cancer research and developments, in line with technological advances such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the European Health Data Space (EHDS), are applied in an ethical, equitable and transparent manner.

In line with the European Union's commitment to fostering open science, this project will actively promote transparency, accessibility, and collaboration in research results. To this end, all publications derived from this project will adhere to recognised open science guidelines and formats wherever possible. We will prioritise sharing results in scientific publications based on open-source formats and using repositories and/or open science promotion platforms, such as those promoted by the EC (e.g. OPENAIRE and ZENODO). We will also take advantage of EU platforms to share our results: Horizon Magazine, Horizon Results Booster, the Horizon Results Platform, the Innovation Radar and the Success Stories.

We will also consider implementable the knowledge and practices from the [FAIRplus](#) project, funded by the [IMI partnership](#) between the European Union (represented by the European Commission) and the European pharmaceutical industry (represented by [EFPIA](#), the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations) as it shares several resources to ensure that data is FAIR – findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-useable.

